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TA'LIMDA TILLARNI O'QITISHNING MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI

**ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЯЗЫКОВОГО
ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ПУТИ ИХ РЕШЕНИЯ**

**PROBLEMS OF LANGUAGE
LEARNING AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM**

MAVZUSIDAGI XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA

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RESEARCH ON MULTILINGUAL TEACHING OF HISTORY COURSES IN CHINESE UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: Multilingual teaching is a teaching mode implemented under the trend of international economic integration. Carrying out multilingual teaching is the urgent need for cultivating compound talents in the new era, especially multilingual teaching of universities has received increasing attention in the world. Among them, history, as a basic discipline, is a major way for the inheritance and development of human civilization. The implementation of multilingual teaching in the history major of universities is not only conducive to development of professional education, but also meets the requirements of social and economic development for history professionals, which is of great significance.

Key words: China Education, Higher Education, Universities, History Courses, Multilingual Teaching.

Annotatsiya: Ko‘p tilli ta‘lim xalqaro iqtisodiy integratsiya jarayonida shakllangan o‘qitish usulidir. Ko‘p tilli ta‘limni joriy etish – yangi davrda kompleks (ko‘p qirrali) kadrlarni tayyorlashning dolzarb ehtiyojidir. Ayniqsa, oliy ta‘lim muassasalarida ko‘p tilli ta‘lim jahon miqyosida tobora ko‘proq e‘tibor qozonmoqda. Tarix fani esa insoniyat sivilizatsiyasini saqlab qolish va rivojlantirishning asosiy yo‘llaridan biri sifatida muhim o‘rin tutadi. Oliy o‘quv yurtlarining tarix yo‘nalishida ko‘p tilli ta‘limni joriy etish nafaqat kasbiy ta‘limning rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi, balki tarix mutaxassislariga bo‘lgan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ehtiyojlarni ham qondiradi. Bu esa o‘ta muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Xitoy ta‘limi, oliy ta‘lim, universitetlar, tarix kurslari, ko‘p tilli ta‘lim

Introduction

With the rapid development of modern science and technology, the global sharing of information and network resources, and the increasingly close international communication, multilingual teaching has received widespread attention from the whole society and the education sector. Cultivating compound talents that meet the needs of China's opening up to the outside world and international cooperation.

Cultivating multilingual talents and political needs, cultural identity, social stability, and avoiding division are the purposes of implementing multilingual education in most countries around the world. Bilingual or multilingual education started earlier in western developed countries, so both teaching theories and practices are relatively mature. Especially in countries with a history of immigration, the representative ones are the United States and Canada.

*Research on the Development of Language Education Policy in Contemporary America*¹ started from the perspective of American language education policy system and introduced bilingual education, Indian language education and foreign language education policies in the United States in detail.

Canada is also a typical multicultural country, its immersion bilingual education model is mature and has been studied by many foreign scholars. Fred Genesee is a representative figure among them. His book *Through Two Kinds of Language Learning: Bilingual Education of Immersion Type and Research* was an authoritative work in bilingual education research, which served as a guide and reference for bilingual teaching research in many countries².

China's bilingual and multilingual teaching research began in the 1990s, with the background of Chinese accelerated opening up to the outside world. To some degree, there are relatively a few books and research theories specifically discussing

¹ Zou Yige. *Research on the Development of Language Education Policy in Contemporary America*. Shanghai: Fudan University Press, 2015.

² Baker, Sylvia Prys Jones. *Encyclopedia of Bilingualism and Bilingual*. Clevedon Multilingual Matters. 1998: 470.

bilingual teaching. Among them, the most systematic book on bilingual education is Professor Wang Binhua's *Bilingual Education and Bilingual Teaching*³.

1. Current Status of Multilingual Teaching of History Courses in Chinese Universities

“Multilingual teaching” means that students’ foreign languages could replace or approach the expression level of their mother tongue through teaching after several stages of training. In China, multilingual teaching means that in addition to Chinese, two or more foreign languages are used as major languages for teaching. At present, most of them are English.

“Multilingual teaching of history” refers to an activity that uses multiple languages to conduct classroom teaching during the history courses teaching process. It regards history teaching as a primary channel, and takes into account foreign languages learning while completing history subject teaching tasks, so that students could train their language skills while learning contents of history subject, so that they could use foreign languages as well as mother tongue naturally and fluently in the teaching process.

Multilingual education in China can be traced back to the “Westernization Movement” in the mid-19th century⁴, and was mainly divided into two categories: government-run schools and church schools. The foreign language courses taught in these schools were mainly English and Russian.

Since the 1990s, multilingual teaching has been booming in China. Then, in the year of 2001, the Ministry of Education of China issued a policy to encourage universities to carry out multilingual teaching experiments. Many provincial and municipal education departments have also put forward some policies to encourage primary and secondary schools to carry out bilingual teaching experiments. Since then, a wave of bilingual teaching has gradually been set off in China. This wave are

³ Wang Binhua. *Bilingual Education and Bilingual Teaching*. Shanghai: Shanghai Education Press, 2003.

⁴ John King Fairbank. *The Cambridge History of Late Qing China 1800-1911*. Beijing: China Social Sciences Press, 1985: 580.

very popular in many provinces and cities across the whole country, and it is showing a trend of prosperity.

Since the beginning of the 21st century, with the rapid development of China's economy, especially after joining World Trade Organization, foreign communication have become increasingly frequent and international competition has become increasingly fierce. The talents needed by society must not only be proficient in their respective research fields, but also be able to conduct extensive international communication. Therefore, it is urgent to cultivate high-quality talents who are proficient in both professional knowledge and foreign languages. It can be said that multilingual teaching is a powerful measure to promote the internationalization of higher education and an inevitable choice for China to keep pace with the world.

From the perspective of current Chinese higher education, the ultimate goal of multilingual teaching in China is to enable students to proficiently use Chinese, English, Russian, Uzbek and other languages in their work and daily life, and to delve into relevant professional knowledge to further enhance students' international competitiveness.

At present, there are mainly the following bilingual education models in China. Firstly, is maintenance bilingual or multilingual education model. Its characteristics is that mother tongue is mainly used for teaching, and a foreign language is gradually used for teaching some subjects. Foreign language teaching is subordinate in terms of time and frequency. The mother tongue and foreign language are basically in a state of separation and basically not integrated.

The second is immersion bilingual or multilingual education. It emphasizes that creation of a foreign language environment, and teaches in a foreign language for part of the time and in some subjects, which is a good integration of mother tongue education as well as foreign language education. This teaching model has the greatest possibility of success and requires schools and teachers to provide students with a better foreign language learning environment and rich resources.

The third is transitional bilingual or multilingual education model. It is a model between the maintenance and immersion education. After entering into schools, students partially or fully use their mother tongue, and gradually transition to teaching only in the second language.

Moreover, another type is embedded bilingual education model. Its characteristic is that the mother tongue and foreign language are used in the classroom at the same time. The proportion of two languages is often determined to the characteristics of different subjects, and there is no restriction on the language used on campus.

Currently, embedded multilingual or bilingual teaching is mainly adopted in Chinese universities, and the foreign languages used are English and Russian in most cases. For example, in history and some science engineering courses, teachers will flexibly use Chinese and English to explain based on the course content and students' foreign language level to help students better understand professional knowledge.

As for the history discipline, although history has a deep solid foundation in China, there is still a big gap between China's historical research and international level. As for the world history research in China, it started late to some extent. At the beginning, it was limited to translation of foreign historical works and the introduction of some western historical theories, but lacked detailed and in-depth analysis⁵. Among them, the research foundation for the history of Uzbekistan and the other four Central Asian countries are in a weak state.

Although Chinese history research in China has formed a complete system after thousands of years of development, foreign Sinology research has also made significant progress in recent decades, so there are many sectors that are worth learning and absorbing by scholars studying Chinese history. From this perspective, whether it is to promote world history research or to promote Chinese history

⁵ Yu Bingfeng. A Practical Analysis of Bilingual Teaching in History Courses of Chinese Universities. Culture And History Vision (Theory), 2010(6): 82.

research, it is necessary to actively participate in international communication and absorb from foreign historical theories and achievements.

Firstly, introducing multilingual teaching of university history courses will help improve the scientific nature of history. For example, Uzbekistan is a neighboring country of China and an important part of China's development to the west. Stable bilateral relations play an indispensable role in maintaining regional stability and China's global strategic balance. Therefore, a large number of Uzbek language talents need to be trained.

At the same time, the implementation of multilingual activities makes history classes more lively and interesting, which allowing students to access original historical materials, and also encourages them to explore and broaden horizons. At the same time, to a certain extent, it enables students get the ability to introduce Chinese traditional culture to foreign countries, introduce China to the world, that is also the goal of multilingual history teaching.

Secondly, multilingual teaching is conducive to cultivating and improving students' comprehensive foreign language abilities. It also helps students form a correct view of history and a scientific spirit of exploration. More importantly, bilingual history teaching helps students keep abreast of the latest historical trends. The development of technology is changing rapidly, and viewpoints of historical research are also constantly being updated. The implementation of bilingual history teaching enables students to keep pace with the latest historical trends, thereby grasping the pulse of world in the development of history discipline.

2. Challenges of Multilingual Teaching of History Courses in Chinese Universities

The shortage of qualified teachers are the biggest problem in promoting multilingual teaching in history courses. It is well-known that teachers are the core element in improving teaching quality⁶. Multilingual teaching requires the use of original foreign language textbooks to explain knowledge by foreign languages in

⁶ Zhang Zhihai. *Foreign Language Teaching and Curriculum Design*. Harbin: Harbin Publishing House, 2022: 88.

professional courses, so it has a higher requirements for teachers' professional level and foreign language teaching ability.

Teachers must not only have good professional knowledge, but also should have a solid language foundation. However, in the current history teaching of universities, the language level and professional knowledge of most teachers are seriously asymmetric, and lots of professional course teachers find it is difficult to teach in a foreign language. For example, in the field of Central Asian history and Uzbekistan history, there are relatively few teachers who can speak Uzbek, that seriously affects the quality and effectiveness of teaching.

There is a large difference in foreign language proficiency among university students. Multilingual teaching requires a high level of basic quality from students. In a sense, multilingual teaching is not just a challenge for teachers, but also for students. Multilingual teaching requires students to have a certain level of acceptance. In particular, some universities, due to the current examination and admissions system, as well as employment prospects of history majors, makes it hard for students majoring in history in local colleges to adapt bilingual teaching. In addition, the hours for each course are short, and bilingual or multilingual teaching and the use of foreign language textbooks will inevitably cause students to have learning difficulties and unable to fully understand professional knowledge.

The lack of suitable textbooks. Textbooks are foundation of multilingual teaching. Without scientific multilingual textbooks, there is no doubt that teaching will lack a bridge connecting teachers and students. If the content of bilingual textbooks is too simple, it will lack the depth of research. If the textbooks are too profound, students will feel afraid and tired of learning, and then lose interest to study.

The teaching plan and method are not good enough. Lacking of scientific teaching plans in universities has restricted the development of multilingual teaching. At present, many colleges and universities still use outdated teaching plans for history bilingual courses, which is inconsistent with reality. As a matter of fact,

in the practice of multilingual history teaching, many teachers have to follow university's teaching plan by compressing the teaching content.

In the meantime, because of the limitations of teaching level, the main form of multilingual teaching is that teachers select some foreign language materials and let students try to translate them first, and then teachers make corrections. The whole process lacks effective interaction and in-depth explanation.

3. Effective Paths for Multilingual Teaching of History Courses in Chinese Universities

Although there are many problems in the multilingual teaching of history, as long as enough attention and appropriate countermeasures are taken, these problems could be effectively resolved. Chinese universities should actively take countermeasures in the following aspects, strive to improve teaching quality of history disciplines, and ultimately achieve good teaching results.

Strengthening teacher training. Recruiting highly educated talents and expanding the scope of multilingual teachers in Chinese universities. It is also important to recruit talents with international education backgrounds. For example, in the aspect of Central Asian history research, those excellent teachers should be introduced from Uzbekistan. Such kind of talents have good foreign language and professional abilities and are familiar with foreign education and subject research. They could directly offer multilingual or bilingual courses, which greatly saves time and training funds.

Improving students' foreign language proficiency. As China is increasingly integrated into global affairs, there is a high demand for a large number of talents who are proficient in multiple languages. Multilingual history courses directly present relevant foreign literature to students, which avoiding misunderstandings caused by the translation process⁷. It could create a real environment for students to

⁷ Hou Congcong. Research on Foreign Language Education and Talent Training in University-Enterprise Cooperation. Beijing: Beijing University of Technology Press, 2023: 149.

the greatest extent possible, thereby deepening their understanding of different cultures.

Improving the quality of textbooks. At present, multilingual teaching in Chinese universities mostly adopts the mode of self-compiled teaching texts and other materials. Its advantages are strong flexibility and low cost, and its disadvantages are that many schools' self-compiled teaching materials could not guarantee professional level. Therefore, in combination with actual situation, history courses can use original foreign textbooks, because it has many advantage, there are more cases and it is very contemporary and participatory.

Flexible selection of teaching models and methods. Chinese universities could create distinctive teaching methods based on their own conditions and students' real levels. Advanced foreign teaching concepts and methods can be introduced into multilingual or bilingual history teaching, such as cooperative teaching model and task-driven teaching method. Through active communication between teachers and students, a win-win situation of knowledge goals as well as the transition to bilingual teaching can be achieved finally.

In short, the implementation of history courses' multilingual teaching of universities will face some difficulties, but it is the general trend of higher education to cultivate compound talents with international competitiveness. There is no doubt that with the joint efforts of Chinese educational institutions and many universities, a multilingual teaching system with Chinese characteristics will be established to promote the diversification of talent training models in universities.

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